

On Data Processing through the Lenses of S3 Object Lambda

Pablo Gimeno Sarroca
Computer Engineering and Maths
Universitat Rovira i Virgili
Tarragona, Spain
pablo.gimeno@urv.cat

Marc Sánchez-Artigas
Computer Engineering and Maths
Universitat Rovira i Virgili
Tarragona, Spain
marc.sanchez@urv.cat

Abstract—Despite that Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) has settled down as one of the fundamental cloud programming models, it is still evolving quickly. Recently, Amazon has introduced S3 Object Lambda, which allows a user-defined function to be automatically invoked to process an object as it is being downloaded from S3. As with any new feature, careful study thereof is the key to elucidate if S3 Object Lambda, or more generally, if inline serverless data processing, is a valuable addition to the cloud. For this reason, we conduct an extensive measurement study of this novel service, in order to characterize its architecture and performance (in terms of coldstart latency, TTFB times, and more). We particularly put an eye on the streaming capabilities of this new form of function, as it may open the door to empower existing serverless systems with stream processing capacities. We discuss the pros and cons of this new capability through several workloads, concluding that S3 Object Lambda can go far beyond its original purpose and be leveraged as a building block for more complex abstractions.

Index Terms—Serverless computing, object storage

I. INTRODUCTION

Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) is a popular cloud computing model, where applications leverage cloud resources via a series of user defined-functions that encapsulate the application code [1], [2]. By controlling all aspects of function execution, cloud platforms deliver a serverless computing model where users do not have to explicitly provision and administer cloud resources. Moreover, FaaS employs a fine-grained pricing model allowing applications to pay for the resources they utilize, while giving the illusion of near-infinite horizontal scaling. FaaS platforms are available in all major cloud providers (e.g., AWS Lambda, Google Cloud Functions, and Azure Functions, to name a few), and have been pulled for a variety of applications such as web services, parallel and distributed computing [3]–[6], and even machine learning (ML) [7]–[9], among others.

Recently, Amazon has introduced S3 Object Lambda, a new capability to better support one of the most common serverless patterns as of today: the processing of data retrieved from the S3 storage service before handing it to an application, a pattern that turns up in many use cases, for instance, to convert across data formats, redact personally identifiable information (PII), or decompress files as they are being downloaded [10], among others. In other words, S3 Object Lambda allows developers to pipe a file through a Lambda invocation on read (i.e., as part of the lifecycle of S3 `GetObject` request), so that applications

will read that file through the “lens” that the user crafted for it. Although this is a very exciting new capability, just because it is there, it does not mean that developers will need it. For this reason, it is felt useful not only to characterize the performance of this new service, but to determine for what uses cases it is ideal and which paths forward can be envisaged. The literature is full of examples showing the emergence of new avenues of research from technology originally developed for other tasks. One recent example of this is the seminal paper by E. Jonas et al. [4], which demonstrated that functions can be leveraged to build a highly-parallel data processing system, spurring the case for serverless data analytics systems [3], [11]–[13]. *Could this happen to S3 Object Lambda?* Nobody knows! But what is important to the community is to find out whether it can be a really valuable addition to the future development of the cloud. For instance, it would be important to learn whether S3 Object Lambda is a near-data processing (NDP) service much like S3 Select [14]. If so, it could be leveraged to push data operations into object storage in a similar manner S3 Select enables files in either Parquet, CSV, or JSON formats to be scanned inside S3 for improved query performance. Pushing computation into specialized processors that are closer to storage have been the design tenet of many commercial products such as the Oracle Exadata server [15] and IBM Netezza [16].

In this paper, we perform the *first* study of the Amazon S3 Object Lambda service. First off, we verify if Object Lambda is an NDP service targeting in-situ operation execution, i.e., as close as possible to the physical dataset locations, rather than transferring the entire raw data to the computing nodes. If true, this opens new research avenues, such as inferring which data operations are “NDP-able” with S3 Object Lambda, which is something that current FaaS platforms cannot do.

Second, because S3 Object Lambda is a serverless offering, we systematically investigate a series of questions related to its performance as well as resource management, such as how fast Object Lambda instances can be launched, function instance reuse, etc., which are fundamental key performance indicators (KPIs) for any FaaS platform. All results are crosscompared to AWS Lambda in order to elicit the differences and overheads introduced by the Object Lambda’s architecture. The analysis includes the variability of the service across regions and over the course of a week. Further, a fault tolerance issue is brought

to light and discussed¹.

Although our original focus was on the chance to revisit the question of how to distribute data processing tasks between S3 Object Lambda and the application servers, we soon realized that the prominent property of this new form of cloud function compared to its predecessors is the ability to *stream* the results to the calling application code logic. While at first glimpse this brand new capability might seem a mere artifact to escape the 6 MB response size quota of AWS Lambda², it creates unique opportunities to efficiently execute ephemeral jobs that would not be handled well by “serverful” systems such as Flink [17] running on a cluster of virtual machines (VMs). The reason is that the the cluster deployment time may exceed by far the job execution time. However, Object Lambdas offer significantly lower startup latency than VMs, and are thus ideal for running short lived jobs.

Unfortunately, this novel streaming feature does not come for free. More specifically, the Object Lambda service charges \$0.005 per-GB of data returned to the application. Clearly, this exposes an interesting trade-off between cost and performance, which we also examine in this research. This is experimentally achieved by comparing Object Lambda against AWS Lambda, and also against PyWren [4], a serverless MapReduce analytics engine.

Summary of insights. Some highlights of our results include:

- We confirm that Object Lambda does not offer “Lambda-in-the-bucket” support, allowing for near-data processing (NDP), thus giving better data locality to these operations. On the contrary, Object Lambda shares the same compute cluster as AWS Lambda, keeping S3 well separated from the compute architecture.
- Object Lambda performs similarly to AWS Lambda. But it presents higher startup times (up to 80%) and response times compared with AWS Lambda due to the two extra hops caused by the S3 Object Lambda Access Point. This extra latency can be hidden by streaming data transfers to the applications.
- Object Lambda streaming feature opens up a new horizon of possibilities (e.g., it allows processing big datasets with small memory functions inline). However, care should be taken to not skyrocket the total cost due to data transfers. To wit, the data transfer cost of decompressing on the fly a 1GiB file can be 100X higher than the compute cost.

We finally wish to realize that more results are given in the body. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II reviews the basic concepts of S3 Object Lambda, and provides basic background information about object storage. Section III details the general measurement methodology. In Section IV, we shed light on the architecture internals of Object Lambda, and its KPIs are assessed in Section V. Section VI explores the opportunities brought by the new capability of Object Lambda to execute ephemeral streaming workflows with only serverless

functions. We revisit related work in Section VII and conclude with Section VIII.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Amazon Simple Storage Service (Amazon S3)

S3 is a highly available object storage service managed by Amazon Web Services (AWS) to persist arbitrary data objects organized into “buckets”. Users can create buckets belonging to any of the available AWS regions, and store, list and retrieve objects from their buckets through either the S3 web console or programmatically, via a REST API or the AWS SDK, available for different languages (such as the Boto3 library for Python). This gives developers access to fully managed, highly reliable and scalable data storage infrastructure through a broad array of programming languages.

Finally, it is worth to mention here that S3 can be seen as a serverless service, in the sense that it scales automatically with no need for explicit provisioning, and is billed based on usage.

B. Amazon S3 Object Lambda

In March 2021, Amazon announced S3 Object Lambda [10], a new serverless capability to add customized code and process data inline from S3 before transferring it to an application. S3 Object Lambda works only with S3 GET requests and uses the power of AWS Lambda functions to modify data as it is being retrieved from the object storage.

The details about the architecture of S3 Object Lambda are vague. The documentation speaks of a new type of S3 Access Point to give the Lambda function access to the original object. But it keeps the opacity on whether the Lambda functions run close to the S3 nodes to exploit (near-)data locality or not. We provide an answer to this question in this work, along with an analysis of the performance overhead of this new access point. What is mentioned in the documentation is that the maximum duration for a Lambda function used by S3 Object Lambda is only 60 seconds. Being this limit 15x shorter than that of AWS Lambda, a critical point is thus to determine the workloads that can be effectively handled by S3 Object Lambda (see §VI).

However, the unique feature of S3 Object Lambda compared with the rest of FaaS solutions lies in its streaming capabilities. That is, the new `WriteGetObjectResponse` API supports HTTP 1.1 chunked transfer encoding to implement streaming data transfers. As a result, the delivery of data to applications can be pipelined with processing, which hides I/O latency (S3 is slow storage [7], [12]) and minimizes the memory footprint. The latter is not a minor thing! The compute cost of S3 Object Lambda depends upon the amount of memory allocated to the Lambda function (as of today, of \$0.0000167 per GB-second), which may save significant money. We say “may”, since CPU capacity is allocated proportionally to the amount of memory assigned to the function³. So, less memory allocation implies a weaker CPU, which may significantly raise the compute cost for CPU-bound tasks.

¹We do not responsibly discard to tell our findings to AWS before this paper is made public.

²<https://docs.aws.amazon.com/lambda/latest/dg/gettingstarted-limits.html>

³<https://aws.amazon.com/about-aws/whats-new/2020/12/aws-lambda-supports-10gb-memory-6-vcpu-cores-lambda-functions/>

In terms of programmability, a NOOP streaming operator that copies the input stream to the output stream can be written using the Boto3 AWS SDK [18] simply as follows:

```
import contextlib, requests, boto3

def lambda_handler(event, context):
    ...
    s3_url = object_get_context["inputS3Url"]
    s3 = boto3.client('s3', verify=False, config=config)
    r = requests.get(s3_url, stream=True)

    with contextlib.closing(r.raw) as file_obj:
        file_obj = iter_chunks(file_obj)

        s3.write_get_object_response(
            Body=file_obj,
            RequestRoute=object_get_context["outputRoute"],
            RequestToken=object_get_context["outputToken"]
        )
```

where `iter_chunks` returns an iterator to yield chunks from the raw input stream. Despite the “beauty” of this new feature, Amazon provides no free lunch and charges \$0.005 per-GB of data returned to the application. As we verify in this research, this cost can skyrocket if care is not taken (§VI).

One “weird” trait of S3 Object Lambda is that the requested object does not have to exist in the underlying bucket. Every `GetObject` request is intercepted by a Lambda function that can artificially generate new data. While this property is useful, e.g., for providing a default response for deleted files, it opens up the door to process streams of data from other sources (e.g., Kafka, ZeroMQ, etc.) without the need to explicitly provision compute resources.

III. METHODOLOGY

We divide our study in three differentiated parts. In the first part, we elucidate some basic details about the architecture and resource management of S3 Object Lambda (§IV). Secondly, we characterize its performance using several metrics such as coldstart latency, response time measured as time-to-first-byte (TTFB), etc. (§V). Finally, we assess the streaming capabilities of S3 Object Lambda by executing several workloads (§VI). Our goal is to draw a thorough picture of the existing tradeoffs of S3 Object Lambda in terms of performance and cost.

A. Performance measurements

For our measurements, we made use of an EC2 `t3.medium` instance (2vCPUs, 4GiB and 5Gbps of network bandwidth) as a client machine. Unless otherwise noted, all the AWS services (EC2, S3, AWS Lambda, and S3 Object Lambda) were located within AWS `us-east-2` (Ohio) region. Function invocations in both S3 Object Lambda and AWS Lambda were performed via the corresponding REST interfaces and public endpoints using `cURL`. The measurements were conducted between Jan. and Jun. 2022. We chose Python 3.8 as the default runtime for the functions and the Boto3 AWS SDK [18] to access Amazon S3 services. All experiments and workloads were run multiple times to achieve statistical confidence and capture performance variability.

The dollar cost of queries is a crucial factor, since it is one of the key reasons to migrate an application from “on-premise” to the cloud. Here we consider all the costs related to Object

Lambda and AWS Lambda, except storage costs which are the same for both services. That is, all the experiments access the same set of files for both Lambda incarnations, thus incurring in the exact same S3 storage costs.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we set out to answer key questions about the architecture of S3 Object Lambda and why they are important.

A. Is S3 Object Lambda a NDP architecture?

While S3 Object Lambda bestows new capabilities, one first question to answer is whether this service was devised to bring near data processing (NDP) to object storage or, contrarily, its architecture is fully disaggregated. The answer to this question is fundamental since if true, developers could use this service as an NDP accelerator similar to S3 Select [14], which allows files in Parquet, CSV, or JSON formats to be scanned inside S3 for improved query performance.

To this aim, we investigated whether S3 Object Lambda and AWS Lambda share the same computing cluster. To do so, we borrowed the simple instance identification strategy from [19], where each function checks the existence of a file named `fID` on the local disk, and if it does not exist, creates this file with a random 16-byte ASCII string filename. As a function instance is not immediately recycled upon its termination, the `fID` file will almost surely exist across subsequent invocations.

We integrated the above logic into a single testing function that we call from both S3 Object Lambda and AWS Lambda. We then performed 50 measurement rounds. In each round, we first sent 100 concurrent requests in AWS Lambda and waited for their termination. Next, we issued 100 concurrent requests through an S3 Object Lambda Access Point configured to call the testing function. If the S3 Object Lambda instances execute on the same computing cluster than AWS Lambda, then these instances should find the `fID` files on their local disks written by the previous AWS Lambda instances.

Results. In all the rounds, all the concurrent S3 Object Lambda requests found the `fID` files on their local disks. Consequently, the functions invoked on demand through S3 Object Lambda do not run on a Lambda cluster “close to storage”, but rather in the same compute cluster than regular AWS Lambda functions. This matches our initial intuition that S3 Object Lambda is not an NDP accelerator, but a “glue” between two disaggregated AWS services: S3 and AWS Lambda.

Other indicators support this finding. For instance, we found that the recycling of idle instances is identical in both Lambda and S3 Object Lambda. Interestingly, we have noticed that the maximum time an instance can stay inactive has lowered down from 27 minutes in 2017 [19] to just 5 minutes at present time. This means that cold starts are much more frequent these days. This result agrees very well with other recent works [20].

B. Inconsistent enforcement of S3 Object Lambda quotas

Because S3 Object Lambda stitches two services together, another question to ask is if this “gluing” architecture is able to consistently enforce any specific quota set for this new service.

Fig. 1: End-to-end **Latency breakdown**.

According to the official documentation, the only new quota is that the maximum duration for a S3 Object Lambda function is 60 seconds. More concretely, the official specs pinpoint that a call to `WriteGetObjectResponse` must be performed before this time limit is reached to successfully send the result of the transformation back to the client.

To check the correct enforcement of this quota, we “cooked up” two S3 Object Lambda functions, which differ in the time that the call to `WriteGetObjectResponse` is performed. In the first function, the call is made after the function sleeps for 60 seconds. In the second case, the call is immediately made, and the function is put to sleep for 15 minutes (i.e., maximum duration for an AWS Lambda function). If S3 Object Lambda enforces this quota consistently, users expect that in both cases the function times out after 60 seconds and an exception is sent back to the client.

Results. After launching 50 times both functions, we noticed that the first function was killed in all cases, while the second one remained active past the 60 seconds, thereby signaling the inconsistent enforcement of this quota. That is, the “zombie” functions were only terminated when the 15-minute duration limit of AWS Lambda was met. This behavior is problematic since developers could inadvertently leave functions executing for more than 60 seconds, even well beyond the point at which the result has been received by the client, which results in extra useless costs for the tenant. However, not all is bad news, since the extra time could be used, e.g., for checkpointing state, and effectively bypassing the 60 second limit.

C. Role of the S3 Object Lambda Access Point

Our previous results suggest that the gluing component of S3 Object Lambda is the new type of S3 Access Point. These access points sit in front of S3 and act as a kind of proxy layer that ❶ intercepts the requests, ❷ forwards them to the remote AWS Lambda cluster, and finally ❸ waits for the invocation to `WriteGetObjectResponse` to transfer (or stream) the results to the client. While the third step could be avoided by sending the results directly from the AWS Lambda cluster back to the client, it is needed for two reasons. One to circumvent the 6MB response size quota of AWS Lambda. The other to enforce the 60 second limit (§IV-B). So apparently, this new type of access point adds two extra hops to access the transformed data.

To corroborate the role of this new type of S3 Access Point, we designed a simple experiment that consisted of calling two identical functions, one through AWS Lambda and the other

via S3 Object Lambda, with the only difference that the Object Lambda function had the mandatory invocation to the special `WriteGetObjectResponse` method before returning. More specifically, both functions downloaded a 1MiB object from S3 and returned an empty body (i.e., HTTP status code 204). By not setting a body, but calling to `WriteGetObjectResponse`, allowed us to check the existence of the extra hop in returning the results by comparison with the AWS Lambda requests (i.e., step ❸ above). Similarly, we recorded the startup time of both functions to ratify the extra hop added by the Object Lambda Access Point before “touching” the AWS Lambda service (i.e., step ❶). Functions were warmed up. To avoid logging inexact timestamps due to the lack of a global clock, we coded a gRPC server to record the timestamps under a common clock.

Results. Fig. 1 shows the latency breakdown of both functions provisioned with 4,096 MB of RAM. Clearly, the startup time (t_{start}) is significantly higher in S3 Object Lambda due to the indirect routing of the requests through S3 (step ❶). Likewise, the delay introduced by the `WriteGetObjectResponse` call is even larger (39 ms), despite setting an empty body (step ❸). The catch here is that the idea of gluing both services together through an specialized S3 Access Point is neat, but introduces performance penalties and quota inconsistencies (§IV-B).

D. What about Streaming?

A unique feature of S3 Object Lambda in the FaaS world is the possibility to stream data transfers. Originally conceived to return large files to the users, the `WriteGetObjectResponse` API supports HTTP 1.1 chunked transfer encoding to stream data transfers. This capability is not accessory. It does not only enable pipelined execution to minimize latency and resources, but opens up the door to building serverless stream processing engines for the first time (§VI).

Those benefits are not free lunch, though. Chunked transfer encoding introduces overheads at the network level. According to the HTTP 1.1 specs, every chunk must start with the number of data octets in hexadecimal, followed by extensions, a CRLF (carriage return followed by line feed) string, the payload and another CRLF. Depending on the amount of data packaged in a chunk, this overhead may become significant, for we wanted to assess in depth how S3 Object Lambda streams data transfers. For this goal, we coded a NOOP streaming operator that simply mirrored the input stream to the output stream. Read and writes from the raw input stream to the output stream were performed in batches of configurable size. The purpose of this test was to check if S3 Object Lambda adapts the size of the HTTP chunks to the application granularity so that users can have fine control over pipelined execution.

For this test, we called the NOOP function to stream files of different sizes, and started up Wireshark [21] (an open-source network protocol analyzer) to capture HTTP traffic and reveal how S3 Object Lambda partitions application data into chunks.

Results. As a first result, we found that the number of octets in HTTP chunks does not depend on the file size. For this reason,

Fig. 2: **Chunked transfer encoding.** Payload size as function of stream batch size for a 10 MiB file.

we only report here the results for streaming a 10 MB file with NOOP performing writes of different sizes. Results are given in Fig. 2. The boxplots show the distribution of the payload sizes (in octets) for the different batch sizes. The numbers above the boxplots list the chunking overhead o , given by $o = \frac{\text{payload_size}}{\text{chunk_size}}$, averaged across all delivered chunks. Three key observations ensue from this figure. First off, Object Lambda creates chunks of the same length as the stream batches written via the call to `WriteGetObjectResponse` up to a certain size. This size is exactly 8,180 octets. This is clearly seen for the 16 KiB batch size, where the payload lengths of the HTTP chunks never rise above the four orders of magnitude (10^4). Second, although the distribution of payload size is peaked around 8,180 octets, or to the batch size for smaller writes otherwise, it shows high variance with a strong bias to small chunks, often of a hundred bytes or less. Finally, the chunking overhead is not significant. For a batch size as small as 128 bytes, this overhead amounts only to 3.5%, which is acceptable for most applications. As a main insight, we see that while developers can have a relative control over the granularity of stream data transfers, the high variance may be problematic for latency sensitive applications (e.g., video streaming).

V. PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT

In this section, we present some basic performance statistics for S3 Object Lambda.

A. Overhead Analysis

To measure the overhead of S3 Object Lambda, we used the time-to-first-byte (TTFB) recorded by the client as a metric. In particular, the client started a time, issued a request and waited to read 1 byte of data from the service. For this experiment, we invoked a NOOP operator in two flavors: batch and streaming. In the batch case, the NOOP function read the complete object from S3 and returned it to the client. In the streaming setting, The NOOP read the object in chunks of 1MiB and copied them to the output stream, so that the TTFB times captured well the overheads associated with the first data chunk. In all cases, the NOOP operator was warmed-up. We played out with multiple object sizes, runtimes and memory allocations.

Results. Fig. 3a reports the results for multiple batch setups with a fixed object size of 1MiB. From this figure, we observe

that the results follow a similar distribution, irrespective of the runtime and RAM allocation. In other words, the TTFB times are always longer than those of Lambda due to the middlebox functions performed by the S3 Object Lambda access points. Notice that Java 11 with 512 MB of RAM setup exhibits a high variability and longer TTFB latencies in both Lambda and S3 Object Lambda. Lambda’s Java 11 runtime is more sensitive to small memory allocations due its higher memory and CPU requirements. Increasing the memory allocation, however, gets rid of this undesirable effect.

Fig. 3b illustrates the TTFB slowdown of S3 Object Lambda related to AWS Lambda for 4GiB NOOP instances. Concretely, the TTFB times are between 1.5x to 1.8x higher for smaller files. But this behavior changes radically for bigger files. AWS Lambda synchronous invocations have a response payload size restricted to 6 MB. Then, the only way to transfer the results to the client is to store them into S3 and later fetch them from the client. This extra step raises Lambda TTFB times, duplicating the latency of S3 Object Lambda for files bigger than 6 MB.

Interestingly, enabling streaming data processing helps S3 Object Lambda cut down the TTFB times drastically. As seen in Fig. 3c, streaming TTFB times keep up with those of AWS Lambda plotted in Fig. 3b. Since the streaming NOOP operator iterates over chunks of the same length, the TTFB delay is also constant across all object sizes. The important finding here is that although S3 Object Lambda is slower than AWS Lambda, stream processing through `WriteGetObjectResponse` API can help mask the latency of the Object Lambda access points.

B. Cold Starts

Next, we turn our attention to cold start delays. As in [19], a cold start refers to the process of launching a new function instance. Cold starts are typically long, of a few seconds, as they may involve the FaaS provider to launch a new container, set up the runtime environment, and deploy the function code. As noted in prior work [1], [19], the high cold start penalty is a notorious roadblock to FaaS vendors as it hurts elasticity. For this reason, we wanted to quantify their impact in S3 Object Lambda and framed in terms of AWS Lambda.

To measure cold starts, we took the difference of invocation time (recorded by the client) and the function execution start time (recorded by the function). We leveraged the gRPC server introduced in the previous section to log the timestamps under a global clock.

Results. Fig. 4 illustrates the cold start latencies of S3 Object Lambda normalized to Lambda values for increasing memory allocations. The Java runtime failed to boot up for the smallest memory allocation of 256 MB. For this reason, we employ the label “Min” to signal in the figure the smallest RAM allocation for each runtime (i.e., 256 MB for Python and Nodejs, and 384 MB for Java). As shown in this figure, cold starts in S3 Object Lambda can be up to only 1.3x higher than those of Lambda. It must be highlighted, however, that this gap shortens when the function instances are run with more memory. The results are consistent in all cases except for Java, where Object Lambda remains 1.2x longer than Lambda, irrespective of the memory

Fig. 3: **Overhead** of S3 Object Lambda measured as TTFB for both *batch* and *streaming* NOOP function instances.

Fig. 4: **Cold start latency** slowdown relative to AWS Lambda for different language runtimes and memory allocations.

allocation. As a main takeaway, we can see that cold starts are not much higher than AWS Lambda, which is great news.

C. Performance Variation

In FaaS platforms, including S3 Object Lambda, tenants are not charged for the precise resources they consume (e.g., CPU cycles), but for the execution time of each function invocation. Hence, it is relevant to investigate the existence of performance variations, across regions (inter-region) and time (intra-region).

Intra-region performance. First, we studied the performance variation of Object Lambda in terms of TTFB and cold starts over a one-week period (168 hours). To quantify the variations, we leveraged the Coefficient of Variation (CV), defined as the standard deviation divided by the mean, which inherently gives a normalized comparison of performance variation. We made use of 4,096 MB NOOP function in batch mode in *us-east-2* region. Results are plotted in Fig. 5. Clearly, this figure shows strong diurnal patterns in cold start delays, with variations that ranged between 10% to 40% depending on time of the day. In contrast, with the NOOP function warmed up, performance was more stable (except for a few spikes), as shown by the TTFB curves. The only exception was for small files (1 KiB), where

CV is of 100% due to a greater impact of the Object Lambda access points.

Inter-region performance. Spurred by the results of the intra-region experiment, we designed a second experiment to assess performance variations (if present) across three geographically distant regions: *us-east-2* (Ohio); *eu-west-1* (Ireland); and *ap-northeast-1* (Tokyo). For each region, we invoked the same NOOP function as above to process a 1 MiB file over the course of 24 hours. For better completeness, we tested distinct language runtimes and memory allocations. Results are shown in Fig. 6. While there are not visible differences in cold starts (except for the Java 11 runtime), TTFB is much more sensitive to region placement. Specifically, Ohio displayed consistently better performance than the rest of regions, exhibiting a 2.43x smaller TTFB than Tokyo for the heavy Java runtime. Beyond concrete numbers, the main takeaway is that the differences in function performance across timezones show that it is feasible to perform spatial placement gaming [22] for Object Lambda.

VI. SERVERLESS STREAMING USE CASES

In this section, we explore in more detail the most relevant property of Object Lambda to our eyes: the ability to pipeline execution (§VI-A) and support complex streaming workflows with only serverless functions (§VI-B).

Note that the importance of this property is not minor. Often, streaming jobs are short-lived and/or bursty. For instance, they alternate between “On” periods with short bursts of events, and long “Off” periods, where no events are present. In these types of jobs, it is very difficult to rightsize the cluster appropriately. Hence, having a way of quickly rightsizing compute resources with “streamable” cloud functions clears the path to efficiently tackle these complicated cases. As shown in Fig. 6b, cold start latencies are well under two seconds for most of the runtimes, which makes them a perfect fit to handle spiky workloads, i.e., one of the main reasons why Lambda and the rest of serverless platforms were built for.

A. Memory-optimized Streaming

As Object Lambda enables pipelined execution, it welcomes the opportunity to mask access latency to S3, while optimizing

Fig. 5: **Performance variation** over the course of 1 week (168 hours) in terms of TTFB and cold start times using Coefficient of Variation (CV) as metric.

Fig. 6: **Inter-region performance variance** for three geographically distant regions: `us-east-2` (Ohio); `eu-west-1` (Ireland); and `ap-northeast-1` (Tokyo).

memory resources. This, however, poses a novel performance-cost tradeoff. On one hand, in the same way as AWS Lambda, the function cost depends on the amount of memory allocated (as of today, of \$0.0000167 per GB-second). But, since vCPU capacity is allocated proportionally to the amount of memory assigned to the function, the overall execution time may grow significantly, in particular, for CPU-bound tasks. On the other hand, Object Lambda charges \$0.005 per-GB of data returned to the client application, which may be prohibitively expensive for IO-bound tasks.

To better understand this tradeoff, we have carefully chosen two complementary workloads. One workload is CPU-bound, and consists of the streaming decompression of `zlibbed` files of sizes ranging between 1 KiB to 1 GiB after decompression. The other is IO-bound, and invokes a `grep` function to return all the lines that contain the word `error` in a HDFS log [23]. This log file was trimmed to different sizes, from 1KiB - 1GiB.

Thanks to pipelined execution, where data from S3 can be processed in small batches, we “**memory-optimized**” function executions. That is, we chose the minimum memory that made it possible to execute each function for every object size, which is the new quality that introduces Object Lambda in the FaaS

world. Each workload was run 100 times.

Results. Performance-cost tradeoff for decompression is given in Fig. 7, and in Fig. 8 for the `grep` workload. In both cases, S3 Object Lambda cannot compete with AWS Lambda in the smaller object sizes due to its higher overhead ($\$V$). This trend changes and the pendulum swings towards S3 Object Lambda for object sizes bigger than 10 MiB. Despite decompression is CPU-bound, Object Lambda outperforms AWS Lambda using smaller memory allocations (≤ 512 MB). This occurs because standard Lambda functions need to pass results bigger than 6 MB to the client via S3. This suggests that memory-optimized Object Lambda processing is useful for files greater than 6MB.

In terms of cost, S3 Object Lambda is more expensive than Lambda for small files as expected. However, as AWS Lambda starts requiring more memory, S3 Object Lambda *may* yield a lower cost. We emphasize “*may*” for one subtle reason. While memory-optimized execution allows Object Lambda to reduce the compute cost, the data transfer cost starts to dominate. This is clear in the `grep` workload, where the size of data transfers is small. On the contrary, the data transfer cost “skyrockets” in the decompression job as the file size increases, making Object Lambda 11x more expensive than AWS Lambda. This leads to

Fig. 7: Zlib decompression performance-cost tradeoff with memory-optimized execution.

Fig. 8: Grep filter performance-cost tradeoff with memory-optimized execution.

Fig. 9: Structure of Parallel Tree Reduction with PyWren.

the general conclusion that Object Lambda is worthwhile for transformations that return modest amounts of data.

We finally notice that if S3 Object Lambda was not limited to 60 seconds, all jobs could have been run with the minimal memory allocation of 128MB. Due to function timing out, we were forced to increase memory allocations to the ones shown in Fig. 7a and Fig. 8a.

B. Streaming Pipelines

During the course of this evaluation, we found that Object Lambda functions can be chained together to implement more

complicated streaming data pipelines. This is possible since an Object Lambda function can invoke another Object Lambda by performing a simple S3 GET API request. The calling Object Lambda then can receive the output from the parent Lambda as an input *stream*, much like it was directly retrieving data from an S3 bucket. There is a subtlety here, though. As intermediate data will pass through multiple Object Lambda endpoints, they will be subject to data transfer costs. As an example, we chose to perform a Parallel Tree Reduction (PTR) over a subset of the GHTorrent dataset [24] in order to calculate the proportion of the different programming languages appearing in Github pull requests. This subset of the dataset consisted of four files, with a total size of 86.2GB.

As a baseline for comparison, we leveraged PyWren [4], a serverless batch processing engine written in Python, famous for pioneering the usage of AWS Lambda for data analytics. PyWren uses AWS Lambda for computation, and S3 for data sharing across functions, i.e., the very same services that glues Object Lambda together. To make a fair comparison, we coded the PTR in PyWren too, reshaping it into a stream processing engine, where Lambda instances were replaced by S3 Object Lambda functions. The structure of the stream PTR is given in Fig. 9. It was composed of three layers of computation. In the first layer, a fleet of 64 functions, each reading chunks of 4MiB from the raw data stream, performed a partial reduction using a tumbling count window of 100k records. In the second layer, 4 functions, one per dataset file, merged the output streams from

Fig. 10: Results for the **stream-like Parallel Tree Reduction** in a subset of the `GHTorrent` dataset.

16 functions in the first layer, continuing the parallel reduction with a tumbling count window, now of 100 records. The partial results from the 4 reducers were ultimately reduced by a single reduce function. Both batch PyWren and stream PyWren used functions with 1GiB of memory in all the 69 functions.

Results. Results are plotted in Fig. 10. We highlight two main results. First, PyWren in streaming mode is more performance-cost efficient than PyWren. On one hand, it presents a shorter end-to-end execution time. The reason is that Object Lambda allows to pipeline I/O and computation phases, whereas each function in vanilla PyWren has to first read, then compute, and finally write intermediate data to S3, which is much slower. To wit, Fig. 10c shows that the time taken to reduce over a count window of 100k records is of only 9.3 ms, which is overlapped with data downloads from S3 in the first tier. In vanilla PyWren this is not possible, and the time spent reading and writing data increases the end-to-end execution time in 20 seconds.

On the other hand, the tree reduction transfers only 16MB of intermediate data out of the original 86.2 GB via the S3 Object Lambda access points. This represents a negligible part of the total cost in comparison to the cost of functions. Hence, our stream implementation ends up beating vanilla PyWren in cost.

Last but not least, streaming capabilities allows processing input incrementally to produce “sufficiently good” results with low latency. While this is not possible in vanilla PyWren, our implementation can distill meaningful results incrementally. In Fig. 10b, we show in terms of the cosine similarity metric [25] how the transient proportion of programming languages in pull requests converges to the true proportion (only available at the end of the job). Interestingly, our implementation yields results with an accuracy of 0.98 in 5.4 seconds. Further, the accuracy becomes close to 1.0 after only 22 seconds, which would have improved the performance-cost ratio by 2x if imperfect results had been sufficient.

VII. RELATED WORK

A myriad of measurements and benchmarks do exist in the literature to evaluate the performance of FaaS platforms, either commercial [19], [22], [26]–[28] or open-source [29]. These works tell altogether how the platforms isolate cloud functions, characterize them in terms of scalability, startup latencies, and resource efficiency, and even show how some platforms (e.g., AWS Lambda) adopt a `bin packing` heuristic to maximize

VM memory utilization [19], among other things. While some results from these works intersect with ours, the specifics of S3 Object Lambda provide unique insights, particularly related to its streaming capabilities and architecture.

Near-data (inline) processing (NDP) from object storage is not novel. For instance, OpenStack Swift [30] and Ceph [31], each implemented their own NDP functionality. In the case of Swift, this was provided through `storlets` [32], small user-defined functions launched on demand (read and write). Ceph provided this functionality with object classes [33] written in Lua. The problem with these systems is that compute resources were co-located with storage servers, thus making the scaling of resources complex. Forgoing the requirement to co-locate storage and compute, S3 Object Lambda can scale better while ensuring that failures of a component do not affect other parts of the system. Although not commercial, some research works could be deemed precursors of the S3 Object Lambda such as Shredder [34] and Zion [35]. Particularly, Zion pioneered the notion of “storage functions” and the separation of storage and compute layers, following a design that closely resembles that of S3 Object Lambda, where the Swift proxy servers took over the role of S3 Object Lambda access points.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Serverless computing is evolving quickly. In this paper, we have conducted the first in-depth study of S3 Object Lambda. Concretely, we have collated fresh insights into its architecture, resource utilization and performance, properly contextualizing them within the specific design decisions (or engineering). But importantly, we have surfaced the novel opportunities brought about by this brand new inline data processing service through several workloads. We conclude that S3 Object Lambda can go far beyond its original aim and be leveraged as a building block for more complex (streaming) abstractions.

The authors provide public access to their code and data at: <https://github.com/pablogs98/Object-Lambda-Benchmark>.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Jonas, J. Schleier-Smith, V. Sreekanti, C.-C. Tsai, A. Khandelwal, Q. Pu, V. Shankar, J. Carreira, K. Krauth, N. Yadwadkar, J. E. Gonzalez, R. A. Popa, I. Stoica, and D. A. Patterson, "Cloud programming simplified: A Berkeley view on serverless computing," 2019.
- [2] I. Baldini, P. C. Castro, K. S. Chang, P. Cheng, S. Fink, V. Ishakian, N. Mitchell, V. Muthusamy, R. Rabbah, A. Slominski, and P. Suter, "Serverless computing: Current trends and open problems," in *Research Advances in Cloud Computing*, 2017, pp. 1–20.
- [3] S. Fouladi, F. Romero, D. Iter, Q. Li, S. Chatterjee, C. Kozyrakis, M. Zaharia, and K. Winstein, "From laptop to lambda: Outsourcing everyday jobs to thousands of transient functional containers," in *2019 USENIX Annual Technical Conference (ATC'19)*. Renton, WA: USENIX Association, Jul. 2019, pp. 475–488. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/atc19/presentation/fouladi>
- [4] E. Jonas, Q. Pu, S. Venkataraman, I. Stoica, and B. Recht, "Occupy the cloud: distributed computing for the 99%," in *2017 ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing (SoCC'17)*. ACM, 2017, pp. 445–451.
- [5] M. Sánchez-Artigas, G. T. Eizaguirre, G. Vernik, L. Stuart, and P. García-López, "Primula: A practical shuffle/sort operator for serverless computing," in *21st International Middleware Conference Industrial Track (Middleware '20)*, 2020, pp. 31–7.
- [6] M. Sánchez-Artigas and G. T. Eizaguirre, "A seer knows best: Optimized object storage shuffling for serverless analytics," in *23rd ACM/IFIP International Middleware Conference (Middleware '22)*, 2022, pp. 148–160.
- [7] J. Carreira, P. Fonseca, A. Tumanov, A. Zhang, and R. Katz, "Cirrus: A serverless framework for end-to-end ml workflows," in *ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing (SoCC'19)*, 2019, pp. 13–24.
- [8] H. Wang, D. Niu, and B. Li, "Distributed machine learning with a serverless architecture," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2019*, 2019, pp. 1288–1296.
- [9] M. Sánchez-Artigas and P. G. Sarroca, "Experience paper: Towards enhancing cost efficiency in serverless machine learning training," in *22nd International Middleware Conference (Middleware '21)*, 2021, pp. 210–222.
- [10] A. N. Blog, "Introducing amazon s3 object lambda – use your code to process data as it is being retrieved from s3," <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/aws/introducing-amazon-s3-object-lambda-use-your-code-to-process-data-as-it-is-being-retrieved-from-s3/>, Mar. 2021.
- [11] J. Sampé, G. Vernik, M. Sánchez-Artigas, and P. García-López, "Serverless data analytics in the IBM cloud," in *19th ACM/IFIP Middleware Conference Industry (Middleware'18)*, 2018, pp. 1–7.
- [12] Q. Pu, S. Venkataraman, and I. Stoica, "Shuffling, fast and slow: scalable analytics on serverless infrastructure," in *16th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI'19)*, 2019, pp. 193–206.
- [13] V. Shankar, K. Krauth, K. Vodrahalli, Q. Pu, B. Recht, I. Stoica, J. Ragan-Kelley, E. Jonas, and S. Venkataraman, "Serverless linear algebra," in *11th ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing (SoCC'20)*, 2020, pp. 281–295.
- [14] R. Hunt, "S3 select and glacier select – retrieving subsets of objects," <https://aws.amazon.com/blogs/aws/s3-glacier-select/>, 2017.
- [15] Oracle, "Oracle exadata," <https://www.oracle.com/engineered-systems/exadata/>, 2023.
- [16] M. Singh and B. Leonhardi, "Introduction to the IBM Netezza warehouse appliance," in *2011 Conference of the Center for Advanced Studies on Collaborative Research (CASCON '11)*. USA: IBM Corp., 2011, pp. 385–386.
- [17] A. Flink, "Flink datastream API programming guide," <https://nightlies.apache.org/flink/flink-docs-release-1.15/docs/dev/datastream/overview/>, Jul. 2022.
- [18] A. W. S. (AWS), "AWS SDK for Python (Boto3) documentation," https://docs.aws.amazon.com/python/sdk/?id=docs_gateway, 2022.
- [19] L. Wang, M. Li, Y. Zhang, T. Ristenpart, and M. Swift, "Peeking behind the curtains of serverless platforms," in *2018 USENIX Annual Technical Conference (USENIX ATC 18)*, 2018, pp. 133–146.
- [20] K. L. Ngo, J. Mukherjee, Z. M. Jiang, and M. Litoiu, "Has your faas application been decommissioned yet? – a case study on the idle timeout in function as a service infrastructure," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.10227>
- [21] Y. Orzach, *Network analysis using Wireshark cookbook: over 80 recipes to analyze and troubleshoot network problems using Wireshark; 1st ed.* Packt Publ., 2013.
- [22] S. Ginzburg and M. J. Freedman, "Serverless isn't server-less: Measuring and exploiting resource variability on cloud faas platforms," in *Sixth International Workshop on Serverless Computing (WoSC'20)*, 2020, pp. 43–48.
- [23] W. Xu, L. Huang, A. Fox, D. Patterson, and M. I. Jordan, "Detecting large-scale system problems by mining console logs," in *ACM SIGOPS 22nd Symposium on Operating Systems Principles (SOSP '09)*, 2009, pp. 117–132.
- [24] G. Gousios, "The ghtorrent dataset and tool suite," in *10th Working Conference on Mining Software Repositories (MSR'13)*, 2013, pp. 233–236.
- [25] A. Singhal, "Modern information retrieval: A brief overview." *IEEE Data Eng. Bull.*, vol. 24, pp. 35–43, 2001.
- [26] H. Lee, K. Satyam, and G. Fox, "Evaluation of production serverless computing environments," in *IEEE 11th International Conference on Cloud Computing (CLOUD'18)*, 2018, pp. 442–450.
- [27] P. Maissen, P. Felber, P. Kropf, and V. Schiavoni, "Faasdom: A benchmark suite for serverless computing," in *14th ACM International Conference on Distributed and Event-Based Systems (DEBS '20)*, 2020, pp. 73–84.
- [28] T. Yu, Q. Liu, D. Du, Y. Xia, B. Zang, Z. Lu, P. Yang, C. Qin, and H. Chen, "Characterizing serverless platforms with serverlessbench," in *11th ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing (SoCC'20)*, 2020, pp. 30–44.
- [29] J. Li, S. G. Kulkarni, K. K. Ramakrishnan, and D. Li, "Understanding open source serverless platforms: Design considerations and performance," in *5th International Workshop on Serverless Computing (WOSC '19)*, 2019, pp. 37–42.
- [30] OpenStack, "Swift," <https://docs.openstack.org/swift/>, 2021.
- [31] S. A. Weil, S. A. Brandt, E. L. Miller, D. D. E. Long, and C. Maltzahn, "Ceph: A Scalable, High-performance Distributed File System," in *USENIX OSDI*, 2006, pp. 307–320.
- [32] OpenStack, "Welcome to storlets' documentation!" <https://docs.openstack.org/storlets/latest/>, 2020.
- [33] N. Watkins and M. Sevilla, "Using lua in the ceph distributed storage system," in *The Lua Workshop 2017*, 2017.
- [34] T. Zhang, D. Xie, F. Li, and R. Stutsman, "Narrowing the gap between serverless and its state with storage functions," in *ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing (SoCC'19)*, 2019, pp. 1–12.
- [35] J. Sampé, M. Sánchez-Artigas, P. García-López, and G. París, "Data-driven serverless functions for object storage," in *18th ACM/IFIP/USENIX Middleware Conference (Middleware'17)*, 2017, pp. 121–133.